

TEACHERS' PARTICIPATION IN SCHOOL ADMINISTRATION: INPUT TO AN ACHIEVED QUALITY OF LEADERSHIP AND GOVERNANCE OF SCHOOL PRINCIPALS

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ABSTRACT

The researcher targeted to determine the relationship between teachers' participation in school administration and the quality of leadership and governance of school principals. The research paper focused on investigating the correlation among the variables of the study. This study utilized descriptive and correlational research designs. The respondents of this study were 133 elementary teachers who are currently teaching in eight (8) schools of Candelaria East District, Division of Quezon, in School Year 2020-2021. The researcher utilized a survey questionnaire through google forms in gathering the needed data. The data gathered indicated that the teacher-respondents have a moderate extent of participation in school administration in terms of curriculum management and teachers' management and a great extent of participation in partnership management. Teacher-respondents perceived that their school leaders have an excellent performance in teachers' development and a very satisfactory performance in leading people and teachers' performance management. It was also supposed by teacher-respondents that their school heads have a very satisfactory performance in terms of transparency and accountability and an excellent performance in terms of ethics. The findings revealed that educational guides significantly predict the quality leadership and governance of school heads. Data analyzed concluded that there is a significant relationship between teachers' participation in school administration and quality of leadership and governance of school heads. The researcher recommends to school administrators on giving more opportunities to teachers to participate in curriculum management and teachers' management. They shall design programs, projects, and activities that aim to encourage teachers' involvement in suggested areas of school administration.

Keywords: Teachers' Participation, Quality of Leadership, Quality of Governance